

Considerations for the provision of synthetic forms of secure data

An ADR UK Synthetic Data Working Group Guidance paper

Executive summary

This guidance document, developed by the ADR UK Synthetic Data Working Group, outlines key considerations for data owners and providers who are planning to generate and share synthetic forms of secure tabular data. It is intended to support the responsible and effective use of synthetic data for purposes such as research planning, tool development, training and collaboration, particularly within Trusted Research Environments (TREs).

The guidance provided in this paper intentionally relates to the provision of synthetic data with **low disclosure risk**. This is typically 'lower fidelity' synthetic data in tabular form that replicates the structure of real datasets but does not preserve statistical relationships between variables yet still has the potential for high utility for a set of defined use cases.

The guidance is structured around a Plan–Do–Check–Act model and is designed to inform organisational policy and practice. Key facets can be summarised as follows:

- Synthetic data should be generated with a clearly defined purpose, including its intended use cases and governance conditions.
- Synthetic data providers and data owners should consult with each other to align on requirements and ensure ethical, transparent practices.
- Generation methods should be selected based on the intended use. Legal permissions and data governance must be established prior to generation, including a Data Protection Impact Assessment where applicable.
- Synthetic datasets should be accompanied by comprehensive documentation detailing provenance, methodology, limitations, and user responsibilities. To support trust and reproducibility, synthetic datasets should be clearly labelled, include disclaimers, and—where possible—be assigned a persistent identifier such as a DOI.
- Checking for quality should confirm that the synthetic data is in fact synthetic and not real data. A variety of measures - including disclosure risk - provide information to give confidence in the synthetic data, which can be included within the documentation.
- Synthetic data providers are urged to use the FAIR Principles and to set out clear guidance for user responsibilities, as well as information for the user about maintenance and updates.
- Synthetic data is an evolving field and further work will be needed to address higher-fidelity use cases and emerging challenges.

Considerations for the provision of synthetic forms of secure data

An ADR UK Synthetic Data Working Group Guidance paper

Authors: Emily Oliver, Sophie McCall, Ryan Bremner, Andy Boyd, Cristina Magder, Puja Myles, Lora Frayling, Elizabeth Pattinson, Jonny Pearson

Acknowledgements: Maureen Haaker, Mike Daly, Sebastian Bacon, Alex Ramage, Lewis Hotchkiss, Gillian Raab, Delyth James, Emma Gordon, Claire Crawford, Mark Elliot, Anmol Arora

Purpose

Synthetic data is an emerging tool for those learning to use and/or planning to use secure data and for collaborators on secure data projects. However, there are important considerations for data owners and providers to ensure they provide synthetic data that meets the needs of the users, remains compliant, and has overall positive impact.

This paper outlines these considerations and serves as a guide to those who aim to provide synthetic data for uses such as:

- **learning to use or planning to use secure data**
- **code and/or tool development**
- **project collaboration**
- **planning research using secure data**

It is aimed at data owners and providers with an interest in improving the efficient use of secure data whilst maintaining its privacy and public acceptability. It is framed using a typical workflow¹ that involves planning, creating, validating and releasing a synthetic dataset. It is expected that the considerations discussed can inform the content of an organisational synthetic data policy.

As the synthetic data field is still relatively new, norms and precedents are yet to fully emerge and develop. Some challenging issues are yet to be fully explored. From this perspective, our guidance is intended as an initial position which can stimulate further thinking and discussion. We expect this guidance to iterate over time as good practice becomes clearer.

Authors of this paper are members of the ADR UK Synthetic Data Working Group² which is an informal gathering of experts across sectors with an active interest in progressing the potential of synthetic data use to support research using secure forms of data.

¹ <https://deming.org/explore/pdsa/>

² <https://www.adruk.org/learning-hub/exploring-the-potential-of-synthetic-data/>

Scope

The guidance provided in this paper intentionally relates to the provision of synthetic data with **low disclosure risk** and potentially high functional utility. This is typically 'lower fidelity' synthetic data in tabular format which seek to preserve the overall structure of a real dataset but do not preserve statistical relationships between variables. As disclosure risk is a central facet of this discussion and could increase with some instances of higher fidelity synthetic data, the focus here is on lower fidelity synthetic data in order to minimise any disclosure risk.

This version of the guidance is aimed at those with the intention of providing synthetic data that are not considered to be Personal Data (as defined under data protection legislation). We include the necessary step to assess this but exclude subsequent considerations which would apply if the synthetic data were classified as Personal Data.

We anticipate future work to expand this approach will consider higher fidelity synthetic data provision (i.e. data which preserves at least some conditional distributions between variables, potentially including relationships across data tables).

Whilst this guidance will need to evolve as synthetic data becomes more widely created and more use cases are tested, we hope it will form a basis for consistency and transparency in provision and policy development.

Definitions

For the sake of clarity and consistency, we provide definitions of synthetic data and related concepts that will be used in further discussions:

Real data are source data – typically in our context they will be about people or organisations – presented as individual rows of information. These can be identifiable, pseudonymised or anonymous.

Metadata are taken to mean information about data, typically provided in 'data dictionaries'. Within the scope of synthetic data considerations, the definition of Metadata is broader than often used and includes published research papers and statistical findings.

Personal Data is taken to mean any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'). In the UK, the definition is set by the data protection regulator, the Information Commissioners' Office³.

Synthetic data is taken to mean data that has been generated using a purpose-built mathematical model or algorithm, with the aim of solving a (set of) data science task(s) and which preserve specific properties of a real dataset without retaining any information about any specific real person. Properly created Synthetic Data are

³ <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/personal-information-what-is-it/what-is-personal-data/what-is-personal-data/>

therefore not Personal data. As literature and discourse on this topic frequently mentions ‘fidelity’ and ‘utility’, these are also defined below.

Fidelity is defined as the closeness in resemblance of the synthetic data to the real data in terms of its overall characteristics and properties. This can be multi-dimensional and include both statistical fidelity and structural fidelity.

- **Structural fidelity** refers to the similarity between the structure of the real and synthetic data.
- **Statistical fidelity** refers to the similarity between statistical properties of the real and synthetic data, such as data variable distributions and correlations between variables.
- **Low fidelity** is typically synthetic data which preserves no distributions between variables.
- **High fidelity** is typically synthetic data that preserves most (if not all) conditional relationships and distributions between variables.

We note that fidelity is best understood as a spectrum rather than a clear binary value.

Utility describes how useful a dataset is for its defined use or set of uses cases. Various tools exist to measure utility. They can be specific to a task, or more general to a set of different uses.

In practice, synthetic data is created with the aim of achieving the fidelity necessary to support a use case while ensuring sufficiently low privacy and confidentiality to permit broad access. Increased fidelity that supports higher utility typically leads to increased privacy risk—known as the **privacy-fidelity trade-off**.

Depending on the purpose of production, synthetic data can be generated using real data or not. Both are included in this definition. Readers should note that synthetic data created from metadata only is sometimes referred to by other terms including dummy, mock, artificial or fake data. For the purposes of this paper, we take these to mean **‘none to low perceived disclosure risk synthetic data’** which are simulated data created from metadata which mirrors the structure and constraints of a real dataset but are not typically calibrated to preserve any statistical relationships.

As this document is intended as guidance for those considering providing synthetic forms of secure data, we have selected the Plan, Do, Check, Act model to sequence and structure the guidance in a logical form.

Phases in synthetic data provision

While motivation and context of creating synthetic data vary widely, the process typically involves four key stages, each including specific steps to ensure clarity, consistency, quality, and effective risk control. The key stages are:

1. Plan: Identify the purpose of synthetic data use and requirements for its characteristics
2. Do: Develop the method for synthetic data generation
3. Check: Assess the synthetic data for quality, labelling, utility and privacy

4. Act: Share the synthetic data under appropriate governance and provide necessary documentation and support.

More generally, one should consider how synthetic data is to be adopted, incorporated and updated across its lifetime, especially as real data sources evolve. In addition to the technical process, there are important meta-level considerations:

Roles and responsibilities

Prior to undertaking synthetic data generation, it is important to decide who will be responsible for each stage and how work will be facilitated, especially for stages that require access to the real data and, thus, require data governance processes. For example, the development, assessment and sharing of the synthetic dataset may each be done in-house by the data holder or third parties with specialised knowledge.

Costs and benefits

Synthetic data generation and release provide value and benefits and incur costs related to time, effort, resources, expenses, utility and risks.

For data users, benefits may include easier data accessibility, improved utility of real data and reduced resource and financial costs. For data holders, benefits may relate to more efficient operations, increased use of data and reputational gains from research.

Costs include expenses incurred as part of creating the data and potential risks of releasing synthetic data, such as privacy. Broader impacts should also be considered, such as carbon costs and research equity.

Sustainability

For cost and carbon sustainability, it is important to consider how resource-intensive the data generation method is and how the size of the synthetic data impacts the costs of planned use cases. For example, it is likely that reducing the synthetic dataset to a proportionate sample is acceptable for some use cases. However, the sample needs to remain representative of the data populations, conditions and variables.

Strategic planning

Planning includes strategic considerations of how the synthetic dataset will be incorporated into workflows and how frequently the data updates are expected.

Once these requirements are clear, one can begin the stages of synthetic data creation.

Stage 1: Plan

- Define the purpose and potential value of the proposed synthetic data and describe expected use cases
- Determine the characteristics that are needed for the expected use cases, how it would be generated for the defined purpose and how the synthetic data will contribute to an effective user experience
- Identify potential risks from sharing the proposed synthetic data and how to mitigate them
- Consider how the synthetic dataset will be incorporated strategically by the organisation into related work, and detail requirements for updates

Purpose

Synthetic data generation should be clear in its purpose and value, with a description of why the synthetic dataset is being produced and what its expected use or set of use cases will be.

Note that reputational risk should not be used as a proxy for disclosure risk. Where synthetic data is used as a privacy enhancing technology (PET), any concerns about perception, trust, or potential misuse should be treated as reputational risks and managed through documentation, communications, and overall governance rather than being framed as a privacy disclosure issue.

As the synthetic dataset is likely to be shared, the conditions under which this can happen should be specified as part of the synthetic data governance, including a decision on whether multiple releases and updates are allowed since this may increase risks to privacy.

In considering its purpose and value, consider the need to generate synthetic datasets which represent different populations, including minority populations, and develop appropriate sampling methods to represent populations accurately.

Requirements

Where real personal data is used to create the synthetic data, there must be a relevant legal basis, approvals and a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) produced for the intended use case. It is the responsibility of the creator of the synthetic data to determine if it is Personal Data or not and therefore whether the use and release of synthetic data also needs a DPIA. Where it is Personal Data, then the requirements of the UK GDPR and the common law duty of confidentiality must be applied. Generators

of the content must refer to the relevant regulatory guidance to inform this determination.

Production methods and sharing mechanisms should be chosen to achieve high utility for the intended use cases. For multiple use cases, it might be necessary to provide multiple synthetic datasets. Each should be viable and be in line with public good research criteria, with appropriate levels of fidelity and accessibility to meet required utility needs.

Consultation

The synthetic data providers should consider whether they will need access to the real data (for checking disclosure risk, even if it is not used to generate the synthetic data). They should consult the owners of the source real data to determine what, if any, requirements the owners have, to inform them about their methods and use case, and to develop appropriate documentation, references and citations.

It might also be necessary to consult the public or to refer to existing relevant public consultations.

In this emerging field, considerations regarding the professional ethics and etiquette of synthetic data generation are still developing. In the absence of established norms, consultation and collaborative approaches are considered key to maintaining support and building understanding for this use of data.

Sustainability

Planning and generation of synthetic data should be considered strategically: the onward financial cost of generating, sharing and using synthetic data, in addition to carbon costs and considerations of research equity should be thought about in the planning stage. Plans for how synthetic data is to be adopted, incorporated and updated across its lifetime are required, including whether a similar synthetic dataset already exists which would be adequate for the intended use. For cost and carbon sustainability, thought should be given to how large the synthetic data needs to be against planned use cases. This is particularly relevant if considering its use for teaching purposes. It is likely that minimising the synthetic dataset to a proportionate sample is acceptable, although, depending on the use case, care should be taken in the methods to ensure the sample content is representative of different populations, lived conditions and data items. Full transparency on the limitations of the dataset should be provided.

Stage 2: Do

- Generation of synthetic data might depend on access to real data and/or quality of metadata available.
- Whilst there are a variety of synthetic data generation tools, some are better suited for certain types of data - for example numeric vs categorical variables
- The documentation should make it clear that the data is synthetic and highlight the ways where the synthetic data is like the real data and the ways in which it differs.

Synthetic data generation method

The creation methods should be documented clearly: whether synthetic data is generated from real data or metadata, or a combination of both, should be specified, along with the exact version (e.g. DOI/date/extract) of the source material used. This will vary by use case.

Since synthetic data will be assessed for utility and privacy, it is helpful to choose methods that are transparent and incorporate privacy evaluations. Transparent methods can be easily inspected to understand what properties of the real data have been retained and the mechanism by which the method generates the data. This is helpful for both assessing the risk of reproducing disclosive information from the real data and reasoning about the fidelity and utility of the synthetic data.

Including evidence of privacy assurances in the method can similarly provide a level of confidence in privacy risk. However, risk assessment of the synthetic data will still be needed after generation. For example, methods can be chosen that first aggregate the real data and/or metadata into a format that can easily be assessed for disclosure risk and then used to sample synthetic data points. For some statistical and machine learning methods, differential privacy can be incorporated that provide a privacy guarantee.

Making the code that is used to generate synthetic data available can support transparency, but it should be subject to a disclosure risk assessment; for example, where a random number generation seed is used, this should not be shared in the code.

Caution should be taken when using large-scale AI models that are trained on unknown datasets, e.g., Large Language Models (LLMs), to generate synthetic data, as they have unknown risks.

The level of plausibility required should be considered according to purpose and use. In some cases, the dataset might need to make sense and be logical (eg dates of death should occur after dates of birth), however for other use cases, more realistic synthetic

data which retains statistical distributions of the real data within a variable or even across variables may be necessary. (Note that this tends to be more relevant to synthetic data with higher levels of fidelity).

Tools

Consider the tools used to make the synthetic dataset and ensure they meet the requirements of the data owner and end user and maintain public trust. Ready-made code and packages (e.g. synthpop⁴) can be used, or bespoke code developed for synthetic data generation. The use of AI techniques (such as Machine Learning or deep learning) for synthetic data generation should also be considered.

Legal Considerations & Rights Management

Availability of data online does not imply rights to copy, scrape, or use it to generate synthetic data (e.g. using academic publications to generate synthetic data from published results, or using online government Open data to produce synthetic data). Before sourcing, synthetic data providers should confirm that they have permission to use the real data for this purpose, and that use complies with copyright, database rights, and any contractual Terms of Service. Where data may be personal or sensitive, ensure compliance with privacy laws, DPIA outcomes, and data-minimisation principles. Beyond legal compliance, synthetic data providers should also apply professional courtesy, respect community norms, avoid uses that could harm individuals or communities, and honour attribution or usage expectations where appropriate.

It is strongly recommended that data owners and providers ensure that a disclaimer is provided with the synthetic data, noting the synthetic nature and the use cases, and applicable limitations.

Synthetic data providers should ensure appropriate data governance and legal permissions are in place to generate synthetic data and that a DPIA has been conducted to assess any residual privacy risks prior to synthetic data release.

Documentation

The method for implementation should be clearly documented and code for generation should be developed, version controlled and stored in line with best practices for reproducibility. Documentation should also detail the version of the real data which was used for method creation.

It is important to provide sufficient documentation including:

- Ownership and contact details for queries and improvements
- A lay summary explaining the synthetic data and information about the original sources; the sources should always be clearly cited, wherever possible with a persistent identifier such as a DOI or if not available URL
- Information about how the synthetic data is generated, whether from real data or metadata, the version of the real data it was created from and the tool(s) and method(s) used to check quality and privacy

⁴ <https://www.synthpop.org.uk/>

- The use cases it has been created for and any limitations that researchers should pay most attention to
- Structural metadata for the synthetic dataset
- User responsibilities in the form of a licence compliance policy⁵ or end user agreement⁶. This should also specify who can use the synthetic data and whether any limitations apply, such as access and storage only for specific geographic regions.

Where possible, a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) should be generated to accompany the synthetic dataset or collection. If this is not possible, guidance should be given on how to provide citation for the use of the synthetic dataset.

Stage 3: Check

- The checking stage confirms that the synthetic data is in fact synthetic and not real data.
- A variety of measures - including disclosure risk - provide information to give confidence in the synthetic data, which can be included within the documentation.

Quality

Quality control measures, such as disclosure checks, should be implemented to ensure that the dataset is indeed synthetic data and not real data, and structurally resembles the real dataset (variable names, types etc).

Labelling

Synthetic data should be appropriately labelled as synthetic, for example by adding a 'synth' suffix to each variable and ensuring that the word 'synthetic' is in the name/header of the file.

⁵ Example of a licence compliance policy: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/app/uploads/cd142-licencecompliancepolicy.pdf>

⁶ Example of a user agreement: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/app/uploads/cd137-enduserlicence.pdf>

Privacy

Appropriate disclosure checks should be undertaken, to ensure that unique values present in the synthetic data do not identify an individual. Where necessary, the synthetic data should be modified to reduce detail or precision, pooling or suppressing rare categories, disguising extreme values and removing replicated unique values as necessary.

The assessment of disclosure should account for the inherent disclosure risk of the real data, previous releases of outputs derived from real data (including previous synthetic data releases), the synthetic data generation method and the disclosure risk of the synthetic data itself.

When the synthetic data generation process is transparent, any stored information derived from the real data should be evaluated for disclosure risk, as this assessment can help determine the potential disclosure risk of the synthetic data itself.

Finally, the synthetic data itself should be assessed for privacy using quantitative measures. There are existing methods and tools that have been developed for this, but currently there is still no best practice, so bespoke methods may also be required.

If disclosure risk of the synthetic data is found to be too high to share under the proposed governance, one should undertake further iterations of method development until it is safe to release. Alternatively, a review of requirements or plans for data governance must be revised.

Utility

Adequate checks of the synthetic data against the real data are required to ascertain, for analytical purposes, where the synthetic data is like the real data and where it is different. For example, comparisons of distribution of variables and presence/absence of relationships between variables. Where possible, use of the synthetic data for its intended purpose should be tested to check for any unforeseen issues which can then be addressed in the documentation and governance.

Further consideration should be given to how the synthetic data will be used alongside or within the current data landscape to achieve optimal impact.

Stage 4: Act

- How should the synthetic data be made available to researchers?
- Consider how any security restrictions might balance against ease of access to the synthetic data.
- Requiring registration to gain access to synthetic data is a useful way of tracking the use of a dataset.

FAIR Principles

Provide the synthetic data following the FAIR Principles⁷:

- **Findable:** Synthetic datasets and collections, including metadata, should be assigned a DOI wherever possible and be discoverable from wherever information about the real data exists. Signposts should be implemented where the real data and synthetic data are hosted in different catalogues.
- **Accessible:** Make the data retrievable via open, standard protocols (e.g. HTTPS/API). State access conditions and use proportionate authentication/authorisation where needed. Ensure document persistence (who hosts it, how long, version URLs metadata); and that they remain openly accessible even if the data are removed. It should be faster, easier and cheaper to access low-fidelity synthetic data that has been assessed to have low privacy risks. As the provision of synthetic data is in itself a privacy enhancing mechanism, it is unlikely that it needs to be housed in a Trusted Research Environment, although this will depend on the risk appetite of the data owner.
- **Interoperable:** Use open, widely supported formats (e.g. CSV, JSON). Provide machine-readable metadata and schemas, e.g. DDI-Codebook/DDI-CDI for rich domain metadata; JSON Schema or CSVW Schema for field-level structure and validation; and DCAT/Dublin Core on the landing page for discovery. Where community norms require proprietary formats (e.g. Stata or SPSS), supply them in parallel with an open format. Adopt community vocabularies/code lists.

⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

- **Reusable:** Provide a clear licence (e.g. CC BY/ODC-BY or a tailored EULA), full provenance and generation methodology (including versions/seeds), quality/privacy evaluation, limitations and intended uses, versioning/changelog, and a recommended citation.

Owner and Provider Responsibilities

Consider whether users should register to use the synthetic data, and how their responsibility and use will be monitored, for example through an End User Licence Agreement (EULA).

Clearly specify what the synthetic data can and cannot be used for, including specific use cases as appropriate. Require explicit reference to the use of synthetic data using its DOI (if available) in any output and provide clear citation guidance for it.

User Responsibilities

Appropriate and persistent credit should be given to the generators of the synthetic data. It should only be used for the purposes intended as outlined in the EULA, with acknowledgment of its use in any shared communication relevant to the use of the data.

Preservation & Maintenance

Synthetic data should be preserved and accessible over time, with clear versioning to support reproducibility. Maintenance should include associated metadata and documentation. Provide a formal route for feedback of quality issues and reporting of resolution. Make provision for the maintenance of the synthetic data, including information on how often it will be updated, where former versions will be stored and their accessibility.

Ongoing management of synthetic data

The *Plan, Do, Check, Act* model is an iterative process. As a rapidly developing field, synthetic data providers should monitor technical advances and the evolving understanding of risk. Implicit to these are emerging issues relating to AI as well as changes in public and stakeholder understanding and expectations of data and synthetic data used for research.

Further work is envisioned on this topic, including the development of evidence on the usefulness of different types of synthetic data.

Whilst the considerations set out in this plan are designed to endure the inevitable evolution of ideas, we anticipate the need for updates and additions in due course.